

October 31, 2018

Corporate Governance and Firm Performance: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan & India

Author's Details

⁽¹⁾M. Umair Nazir ⁽²⁾Madiha Khan ⁽³⁾M. Hammad Ather

Abstract

What mechanism would use to measure the corporate governance? There has investigated the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance in Pakistan and India. Board Size, CEO duality and Institutional Shareholders, have selected as the corporate governance variables further ROA and ROE as measures of firm performance. Data extracted from the annual audited reports of 100 listed Non-Financial Companies from Pakistan and Indian Stock Exchange for the 2012-2015 financial years. This study sheds light for the finding of relationship. Regression results indicate that board size has negative relation with firm performance. This suggests that small board is related with the higher performance of firm. Moreover, the results relate that the separation of CEO and Chairman has a significant positive relationship with the firm performance in both countries. The non-executive directors on the board are not associated with the firm performance of the listed companies in Pakistan and India.

Keywords: Board Size, Corporate Governance, Firm Performance. Ownership structure

1-Introduction

The Corporate governance and its effect on the corporate financial performance is much debated area. In the last decade, empirical research has emerged significant relationship between various corporate governance aspects and corporate financial performance in the developed countries context. Moreover, corporate governance mechanism and firm performance has gotten more attention of the researchers in the developing regions, such as Pakistan and India. This study is a shed light for the corporate collapse and scams. Poor protection of the corporate shareholders resulting from the poor corporate governance practices. Indeed, to improve and reform the corporate governance practices in the region. Weak corporate governance practice leads to financial scam (Berkman et al., 2009).

Current Corporate governance rules, principles, structures and mechanism has been unsuccessful to prevent the financial scams (Sun et al., 2011). The firms with weak corporate governance practices have to face more agency problems and manager opportunistic behavior (Core et al., 1999). Agency theory has debated, that the managers are not careful about the money of shareholders as with their own money (see Letza, 2004). Further, the theory explains that the main objective of the directors to assure the shareholders that their funds are using for the achieving outcomes in the shareholders' interest (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997). Steward theory, theory discloses strong relationship between the shareholders satisfaction and the organization success. Steward theory describes, protect shareholders wealth and maximize the wealth of shareholder through the firm performance. The stakeholder theory suggests that a corporate should provide a balance between the interests of its various stakeholders (Abrams, 1951). John and Senbet (1998) had provided a main theme of stakeholder theory that discussed about the presence of many parties with competing interests within the operations of the company. The resources dependency theory describes the agents as resources who provide the information about social and business networks. These agents provide information about the other organization, so this information can be used for the firm's benefit. This theory discloses that the importance of corporate governance. All the theories of corporate governance give more attention toward an effective governance system, which include the apportionment of board of directors both executive and non-executive directors. In the last couple of decades, there has been given more intensity of research on the relation between corporate governance and firm performance. But this issue has been investigated in developed countries (Hermalin and Weisbach, 1991; Kang and Shivdasani, 1995; Gompers et al., 2003; Judge et al., 2003; Barnhart et al., 1994; Bauer et al., 2004; Christopher, 2004; Bhagat and Bolton, 2008; Guest, 2008). The empirical work on this issue is still less for the developing countries like Pakistan and India. Due to the opaque discloser of corporate governance practices in

October 31, 2018

the region. Previous studies on India were either on small samples studies or on a cross sectional data (Dwivedi and Jain, 2005; Ghosh, 2006; Garg, 2007; Jackling and Johl, 2009 ; Javid, Attiya Y and Iqbal, Robina, 2009). The backdrop of this study is to determine the Impact of corporate governance on firm's performance for large sample of Indian Manufacturing industry. Therefore, in this study we add more information for both countries to the existing literature. Firstly, we make the dataset of representative firms of Pakistan and Indian, our empirical study concentrate on a large number of companies covering both countries companies. Secondly, we separate from the conventional system of prior studies of literature and instead of focusing on a single measure framework. In this study, utilize a range of measures of corporate governance including Board Size, Independent Board Members, Institutional Shareholders and CEO duality. Endogenous factor and regression results are more sensitive toward the use of estimation techniques.

We use several techniques for the testing of relationship. Which include Two-Stage Least Squares (2SLS) which effectively to reduce the problem of Endogeneity and simultaneity bias and second test is Panel Corrected Error Estimations (PCSE) test which overcomes the problem of heterogeneity and serial correlation. This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature on the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance; Section 3 discusses the sample selection, its characteristics, data sources, construction of hypotheses and model specification. Section 4 presents the empirical results on the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance and discussion and future implication thereof.

2-Review of Literature

The literature review examines the relationship between firm performance and corporate governance some subset of several proxies, such as insider shareholding ownership, board composition, board size, executive compensation, and other board tasks (see, e.g., Jensen, 1993; Yermack, 1996; Dalton et al., 1999; Coles and Hesterly, 2000; Elsayed, 2007; Bhagat and Black, 2002). Some studies focusing on corporate governance composite index. For example, Gompers, Ishii, and Metrick (2003) and Core et al. (2006) construct a governance index (G-index). Therefore, in this study, we find the relation only the main proxies of corporate governance and their linkage with firm performance. Later, we provide a review of findings of Pakistan and Indian studies. The variable of corporate governance board size has been debated in many studies (Lipton and Lorsch, 1992; Jensen, 1993; Yermack, 1996; Dalton et al., 1999; Hermalin and Weisbach, 2003; Neville, 2011). Different studies supported smaller boards, for example, Lipton and Lorsch, (1992); Jensen (1993); Yermack, (1996), while other different studies favored large board size because it provide a great monitoring and effective decision-making, for instance Pfeffer, (1972); Klein, (1998); Adams and Mehran, (2003); Anderson and Reeb, (2003); Coles, et al., (2008). Small board is more effective than large board size because large board size face problem of social loafing and free riding (Lipton and Lorsch 1992). When board increases, freeriding increases, and the output of the board is decreased. This claimed by Jensen (1993) who supported small board size that it towards a better decision-making due to more coordination and less communication problems. Small board size is associated with higher firm value (Yermack 1996) and (Eisenberg et al., 1998).

Large board size has to confront with the problem of communication and cohesiveness, which lead to conflicts (O'Reilly et al., 1989). While the other hand the type and magnitude of the firm needs to have large board due to the diversified firms operations might demand greater advice and discussion (Hermalin and Weisbach, 1988; Yermack, 1996) and therefore, larger boards are required for such firms. An essential trend seen in the corporate boards, after the scandals they increase the size of board with outside directors. Baysinger and Butler (1985) and Rosenstein and Wyatt (1990) have claimed that market premium firms for electing outside directors. Brickley et al., (1994) argued that the relationship between percentage of outside directors and stock-market backlash and established positive relationship between outside directors and stock market reaction. Distribution of outside director does not affect firm performance (Yermack 1996). There was no relation between the outside directors and various firm performances (Forsberg 1989). Consistent with the literature Hermalin and Weisbach (1991) and Bhagat and Black (2002) were failed to determine the relationship between board composition and firm performance. The board members increase due to the political pressure so many outside directors in the board; those cannot any improvement in the company performance (Agrawal and Knoeber

October 31, 2018

1996). The board has an essential impact on firm performance and meetings are required for the effectiveness of boards' objectives (Zahra and Pearce, 1989). When board of directors reconcile frequently, they share more concerned issue and monitor the managers adequately, so they can perform their job orders in more effective way by better coordination and in harmony for the increasing the shareholder wealth (Lipton and Lorsch, 1992). Continue with existing literature, Conger et al., (1998) suggested that meeting time of the board is a basic resource for increasing the board effectiveness and better decision making. But the other hand the cost affix with board meeting, as like managerial time, travelling expense, fee and other resources for the directors (Vafeas, 1999). Lipton and Lorsch (1992) and Jensen (1993) mentioned that the limited time applicable for the meetings of directors, might not be sufficed, for generous dialogue. In contrast, the board of directors should be inactive and they are to become active at the time of predicament Jensen (1993). There is soaring debate on the affair of CEO duality and firm performance, but the many studies affirm conflicting results (see e.g., Rechner and Dalton, 1991; Boyd, 1995; Balingaet al., 1996; Coles and Hesterly, 2000; Elsayed, 2007; Bhagat and Bolton, 2008). The CEO-Chair separation has significantly positive correlation with firm performance Bhagat and Bolton (2008). The CEO possessed both chairs then firm performance improves Boyd (1995).

Firms have outperformed that depend on the CEO separation rather than those have CEO duality Rechner and Dalton (1991). Many studies found no relationship between the CEO duality and separation (Daily and Dalton 1997; Dalton et al., 1998). Actually, separation of CEO and chairperson in order to misleading effort Daily and Dalton (1997). However, the proxies of the corporate governance, ownership controls and institutional shareholding are also important dimensions of the firm performance. How ownership control and institutional shareholders promote in firms in an developing economy as Ghana, forward that these systems are very important for improving corporate governance practices Agyemang and Castellini (2015). Kyereboah-Coleman (2007) argued that institutional shareholding increase the market value. While the other hand, the corporate governance has been effect on firm performance (viz., EPS, ROA and ROE), the institutional investors has no positive relationship with the firm performance Mashayekhi and Bazaz (2008). Moreover, many empirical studies have mixed suggestions about the corporate governance and firm performance.

On the contrary, some studies (e.g. Bathala and Rao, 1995; Hutchinson, 2002 and Baueret al., 2004) expressed a negative relation between the corporate governance and firm performance. Further, some studies have proclaimed that no significant relationship between corporate governance and firm performance (e.g., Hermalin and Weisbach, 1991; Park and Shin, 2003; Prevost et al., 2002; Singh and Davidson, 2003; Young, 2003).

There is minor study empirically tested for the relationship between the corporate governance and firm performance in the context of Pakistan and India. Persistent with the literature, the finding on Pakistan and India are very mixed, for relationship between Corporate governance and the firm performance, for instance results of Dar, L., Naseem, M. A., Niazi, G. S. K., & Rehman, R. U. (2011) and Muhammad Ali (2016) for Pakistan and Kathuria and Dash (1999) and Jackling and Johl (2009) for India.

Board size and firm performance estimated a positive relation Dwivedi and Jain (2005). While the other hand, board size and the corporate governance has negative relation directors has a positive relation with the firm performance Ghosh, (2006). Recent study, directors have negative relation with performance due to they have multiple position in different firms Jackling and Johl (2009). The above arguments suggest that empirical studies on corporate governance and firm performance sustain a clashing set of results. Mystify that how corporate governance discloses to firm performance after considering many studies.

3. Research Design and Methodology

In this part, we debate about on data root, model selection for the empirical estimation to find out relationship between corporate governance and the firm performance.

3.1 Data

The data for the research is extracted from Annual audited reports of the companies, from the region of Pakistan and India. There are 100 firms selected from both stock exchanges, by proportion of 40 from Pakistan stock exchange & 60 from National Stock Exchange of India.

October 31, 2018

For this study, we use Return on asset (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE), which techniques were used by Arora, A., Arora, A., Sharma, C., & Sharma, C. (2016) for measuring the firm performance.

For measurement of the corporate governance, we use the corporate governance proxies including board size, independent board members, and CEO duality, Sum of Five Largest Shareholders (institutional shares holders). The control variables are Leverage (defined as the ratio of debt and to total assets), Firm size (natural Log of total Assets).

3.2. Variables Construction and Empirical Hypotheses

This section brings analysis on explanatory variables and their relationship with gauge of firm's performance.

3.2.1 Board Size (BS)

It is broadly discussed that large boards size are less effective and accessible to control for the CEO's. The cost of the coordination and transformation are also higher in large boards and create hurdles for decision-making (Anderson and Reeb, 2003; Coles et al., 2008). In contrary is that smaller boards size lead to better firm performance and decrease the free-riding (Lipton and Lorsch, 1992; Yermack, 1996; Eisenberg et al., 1998). In this study, we use the board size for measuring the relationship between board size and firm performance.

Hypothesis 1: The board size is positively related to firm performance.

3.2.2 Board Independence (BI)

The involvement of independent directors on corporate boards is to create an effective system for the distinction between management and shareholders. The board becomes more independent and effective if it has higher portion of Non-Executive directors John and Senbet (1998). On the other hand, negative relation between the board independent directors and firm performance (Bhagat and Bolton, 2008). Therefore, we suppose it has positive impact on firm performance. The fraction measures of independent directors serving in the board of the company. It is measured by dividing the number of non-executive independent directors by total directors. We investigate the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2: Board Independence has a positive relationship with firm performance.

3.2.3 CEO Duality (CED)

There is clash of interest and more agency costs when the CEO possesses the both chairs at same time and has suggested the both position occupied by two different person not by same person (Berg and Smith, 1978; Ehikioya, 2009). When CEO possesses the doubles authority as CEO and Chairman, it permits CEO the freedom to take decisions without any influence. Initially empirical results disclosed that CEO duality has no effect on the corporate performance Elsayed (2007). The CEO duality is added in the model to analyze the CEO duality impact on corporate performance. The proxy of CEO duality takes dummy variable (when CEO possesses both chairs as board chair 1 and 0 otherwise) as a specification of corporate governance variables. In order to following hypothesis to test:

Hypothesis 4: CEO duality is negatively related to firms' performance.

3.2.4 Institutional Ownership

The type of ownership is an essential aspect of governance structure and gives as an extra overseeing device on the affairs of the firm and domination on the firm performance. So it is considered that institutional ownership has positive relation on the firm performance. In this study the measurement of the institutional shareholder as total shares held by institutions divided by total number of shares of the company (IO). We test as follows hypothesis:

Hypothesis 5: Institutional shareholding is positive impact on firms' performance.

3.2.6 Control Variables

Our model comprises some influential firm-specific aspects to control the model. It includes firm size measured using the natural log of Assets, leverage, ratio of total debt to assets (Lev). These variables also have taken by (Akshita Arora Chandan Sharma, 2016).

3.3 Empirical Model and Estimation Techniques

To test the impact of corporate governance on firm performance, we select the following base model:

October 31, 2018

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X + \beta C + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where Y demonstrate firm performance, X is a vector of corporate governance variables and C is a vector of control variables for firm i at time t. α_0 and β_s are intercept and parameters to be estimated, respectively. ε_{it} is the error term.

In the given model firm performance is denoted by Y and X is representing the Corporate Governance variables, as well as C represent to control variables for firm i at time t. α_0 and β_s are intercept and parameters to be estimated, respectively. ε_{it} is the error term. The corporate governance variables present a problem of endogeneity (Black et al., 2003). Further, the variables of corporate governance are affected by the past performance of the firm, which is related to dynamic endogeneity (Wintoki, Linck, and Netter, 2012).

3.4 Testing for violation on panel error assumptions.

As per prior studies that panel data frequently associated with heteroscedasticity, serial correlation. Hence, these complications are needed to be corrected (Beck and Katz, 1995). Therefore, we will perform further test to verify the assumptions.

3.5 Testing for Heteroskedasticity

Regression disturbance that variance are not constant. Heteroscedasticity present in the both type of Cross-Section and Time-Series data”. Due to the Heteroskedasticity results to be inefficient (Baltagi, 2005). Therefore, a modified Wald test is held to check Heteroskedasticity in the disturbance term of the fixed effect model (Baum, 2001).

3.6 Modified Wald test for group wise in fixed effect regression model

Test for Return on Assets for Pakistan firms

Ho: The error term is homoscedasticity.

<p>chi2 (40) = 5.3e+0 Prob>chi2 = 0.0000</p>
--

The null hypothesis is that the error term is homoscedasticity. The above table depicts that (P = 0.000) which strongly rejects the null at least at 1% level, demonstrates the presence of Heteroskedasticity.

3.7 Test for Return on Equity for Pakistan firms

Ho: The error term is homoscedasticity.

<p>chi2 (40) = 1.0e+13 Prob>chi2 = 0.0000</p>

The null hypothesis is that the error term is homoscedasticity. The above table depicts that (P = 0.000) which strongly rejects the null at least at 1% level, demonstrates the presence of Heteroskedasticity.

3.8 Test for Return on Equity for Indian firms.

Ho: The error term is homoscedasticity.

<p>chi2 (59) = 3.5e+08 Prob>chi2 = 0.0000</p>

The null hypothesis is that the error term is homoscedasticity. The above table depicts that (P = 0.000) which strongly rejects the null at least at 1% level, demonstrates the presence of Heteroskedasticity.

3.9 Test for Return on Assets for Indian firms.

Ho: The error term is homoscedasticity.

<p>chi2 (60) = 9.3e+06 Prob>chi2 = 0.0000</p>

The null hypothesis is that the error term is homoscedasticity. The above table depicts that (P = 0.000) which strongly rejects the null at least at 1% level, demonstrates the presence of Heteroskedasticity.

3.10 Testing for serial correlation

October 31, 2018

Time series data frequently has autocorrelation problem or serial correlation of the disturbance across periods (Green, 2012, p. 903). Serial correlation has a problem for the linear panel data due to the presence of standard error biased likewise regression coefficient consistent but inefficient (Baltagi, 2005; Drukker, 2003). As Wooldridge (2002), a test for serial correlation is used in panel, temporal unit is equal to or larger than.

So here on the assumption, we deploy the test of Wooldridge as follows for both countries firms.

In this section, we represent the results of the dependent and independent variables. Further, to measure the impact of corporate governance variables on the firm performance. Firstly we check the Heteroskedasticity and serial correlation in the data as following.

3.10.1 Test for the serial Correlation

As following test for the serial correlations, to check the data serial correlation for the data corrected estimations

Ho: There is no serial Correlation.

Return on Equity for Pakistan Firms	Return on Assets for Pakistan Firms
F(1, 39) = 16.296 Prob > F = 0.0002	F(1, 39) = 8.964 Prob > F = 0.0048

The above Table shows the statistical F = 16.296 & 8.965 (P = 0.0002 & 0.0048) as the evidence to reject the null on 1% level of significance.

Return on Equity for Indian Firms	Return on Assets for Indian Firms
F(1, 58) = 7.062 Prob > F = 0.0102	F(1, 59) = 1.305 Prob > F = 0.0257

The above Table shows the statistical F = 7.062 & 1.305 (P = 0.0102 & 0.0257) as the evidence to reject the null on 5% level of significance. So as per above results of Wooldridge test we reject the null hypothesis.

The OLS methods could lead biased and inconsistent results (see Maddala and Lahiri, 2009). It is probably that model obstacle of omitted variable biasness in estimation. Whenever the panel errors are heterokedasticity and auto correlated, so neither fixed nor random effects model is sufficient (Baltagi 2005). Further, the problem of spatial and temporal correlation in panel structure, cannot investigate by the common methods (Reed and Ye, 2011). Therefore, in this study this problem can be solved through either panel corrected standard error (PCSE) method or Parks’ Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS). These measurements can overcome with the problem of serial correlation and heteroskedasticity. Yet, PCSE is preferable to FGLS in provision of Standard Errors (Beck and Katz, 1995). However, PCSE is more efficient model than OLS for the accurate investigating the relationship” (Beck and Katz, 1995, p.641). Additionally, Parks’ FGLS is a good estimation method for estimation but it is not good for the performing of confidence intervals (Reed and Ye 2011). PCSE is better choice for the estimation of complicated error structures. Therefore, in this regard we use the PCSE Model use to overall fitness in our panel data (Kawai 2007) & (Yihua 2010).

3.11 Panel-corrected standard errors (PCSE).

As following PCSE test for the relationship between the impact of corporate governance practices on the firm performance.

Indian Firms Results

Return on Assets as tool is using for the measuring the relationship between corporate governance practices impact on the firm performance.

Table 1 shows the results of the relationship between the dependent variable Return on Assets (ROA) and explanatory corporate governance variables with respect to R-squared value 0.0830.

The association between the board size of the firm with the firm performance is positive correlated with the coefficient 0.013231 while the p 0.076 value insignificant in the Indian companies which means that if the board

October 31, 2018

size increases the performance of the firm will be increased. CEO duality (CED) has positive correlation with coefficient 0.0739 and the p value 0.000 is highly significant which means Indian firms will perform better if their CEO's have possessed one position. If the same person possess both chairs CEO and chairman at same time. It will lead to the lower financial performance of Indian firms. Ownership structure is negative correlated with the return on assets with the p value 0.720. If the investment of different institutions increases it decreases the firm financial performance. Next proxy is firm size (FS) is positive correlated with the return on asset (ROA) as accounting proxy for measuring the firm performance. Leverage is positive correlated with the return on assets while Independent board members are negative correlated with the return on asset.

Linear regression, correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs)

Table No: 1

Group variable: compny	Number of obs =	240
Time variable: year	Number of groups =	60
Panels: correlated (balanced)	Obs per group: min =	4
Autocorrelation: no autocorrelation	avg =	4
	max =	4
Estimated covariances =	1830	R-squared = 0.0830
Estimated autocorrelations =	0	Wald chi2(6) = 296.72
Estimated coefficients =	7	Prob > chi2 = 0.0000

	Panel-corrected					
ROA	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
BS	.013231	.0074461	1.78	0.076	-.0013631	.027825
CED	.0739651	.0112781	6.56	0.000	.0518606	.0960697
OWN	-.0151814	.0423297	-0.36	0.720	-.098146	.0677832
FS	.0075544	.0042708	1.77	0.077	-.0008163	.015925
LVG	.0180609	.0049854	3.62	0.000	.0082896	.0278322
IBM	-.0022146	.0034359	-0.64	0.519	-.0089488	.0045196
_cons	-.1609693	.0493146	-3.26	0.001	-.2576242	-.0643145

Return on Equity.

Return on Equity is another tool to measure the firm performance. Here we used for the measurement of the association between the dependent variable Return on equity and Corporate Governance variables in Indian context as following.

Table 2 shows results of Indian firms for the dependent variable, as accounting calculated Return on equity a firm performance tool, the association between the dependent variable return on equity (ROE) and independent variables the board size (BS) is positive correlated. CEO duality is positive correlated with highly significant value 0.001. Ownership structure is also positive correlated with the dependent variable and as Firm size with coefficient 0.034698 is positive correlated. Further, Leverage (LVG) is negative correlated with firm performance with coefficient of -0.524196 with highly p value 0.006. Last one is independent board members of the companies have negative association with the firm performance with coefficient value -.0319009. These proxies are interrelated with the firm performance in Indian context.

Table No: 2

October 31, 2018

(IBM) is negative associated with the Firm performance (ROA) with coefficient -.0387869 and p value 0.000 highly signified. CEO Duality is negative correlated with coefficient -1.036083 and significant value 0.093. ownership structure with coefficient of .298373 is positive related with the return on Asset and p value is .015 which is highly significant. Leverage is negative correlated with the coefficient value -.3301502 and p value is .0.000 highly significant with the firm performance. Firm size (FS) is negative correlated with coefficient -.0399134 with the firm financial performance as per accounting tool return on Asset.

Table No: 4

Linear regression, correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs)						
Group variable: comp			Number of obs	=	160	
Time variable: years			Number of groups	=	40	
Panels: correlated (balanced)			Obs per group: min	=	4	
Autocorrelation: no autocorrelation			avg	=	4	
			max	=	4	
Estimated covariances	=	820	R-squared	=	0.0506	
Estimated autocorrelations	=	0	Wald chi2(6)	=	1052.08	
Estimated coefficients	=	7	Prob > chi2	=	0.0000	

	Panel-corrected					
ROE	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	

BS	-.69579	4.136146	-4.04	0.000	-24.80248	-8.58909
IBM	-.842394	7.485179	-1.18	0.237	-23.51307	5.828286
CEDU	-.35311	7.693748	-13.04	0.000	-115.4325	-85.27357
OWN	-.2304	92.7785	-2.70	0.007	-432.0729	-68.3879
LVG	-.36616	29.28118	-3.29	0.001	-153.7562	-38.9761
FS	-.7338	8.423204	-1.39	0.164	-28.24298	4.775373
_cons	570.4571	105.8194	5.39	0.000	363.0548	777.8593

The table 4 shows the results for the firm performance as on accounting calculation of the return on equity. ROE is negative correlated with the Board Size (BS) with coefficient -.69579 with the highly significant value 0.000. its mean board size of the firm when decreases it leads to better financial performance of the firm with respect to Dependent variable return on equity. Independent Board Members (IBM) variable has negative association with coefficient -.84239. CEO duality (CEDU) is negative correlated with the Return on equity with coefficient -.353 while p value is highly significant 0.000. Ownership Structure (OWN) is negative associated with the return on equity with the coefficient value -.2304 and p value is significant 0.007. Leverage (LVG) is negative correlated with the return on equity with coefficient -.366 and p value is .001. Firm Size is negative correlated with the coefficient -.7338 with return on equity.

3.12 Endogeneity Problems & Two-Stage Least Squares (2SLS) Regression Analysis.

Endogeneity is a major issue in the measurement of the relationship among variables, mostly in the social sciences subject because these subjects are interrelated with the behavior of the peoples so in some studies. It is difficult to measure the accurate parameters of the people behavior, as well as it is not easy way to construct a laboratory for social sciences research likewise natural sciences. Further, many studies are biased due to the Endogeneity problem. There is an essential reason for the endogeneity when the investigator self-selects the sample rather than on the basis on random selection. Further, researcher is omitted variable or may due to the measurement error. The Endogeneity issue is significant in the research the effect of corporate governance on the firm valuation Denis (2001). As Himmelberg et al. (1999) describe that CEO may be selected endogenously by the parameters of the firm, we also use the two-stage instrumental variable locate this Endogeneity issue for CEO duality. The industry average CEO ownership is used as the extra exogenous variable in the first stage. So as per above discussion we have selected the CEO as instrumental variable. Pakistan Firms Results for Endogeneity Test Following tables shows the results about the Endogeneity for the Pakistan firms.

October 31, 2018

Instrumental variables (2SLS) regression (ROA).

Table No: 5

Wald chi2(5) = 16.92 Prob > chi2 = 0.057 R-squared = 0.0473 Root MSE = .71779						

ROA	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z 	[95% Conf. Interval]	

IBM	.0839397	.1745077	0.48	0.631	-.2580891	.4259685
BS	.0127289	.0421484	0.30	0.763	-.0698805	.0953383
NST	.4573689	.3412307	1.34	0.180	-.2114309	1.126169
LVG	-.2702726	.1302283	-2.08	0.038	-.5255154	-.0150298
FS	-.0819875	.0858822	-0.95	0.340	-.2503135	.0863384
_cons	.3398035	.491173	0.69	0.489	-.622878	1.302485

We are testing the Endogeneity factor in the equation with dependent variable Return on Asset (ROA) with respect to independent variables of corporate governance.

Null Hypothesis: There is no Endogeneity Factor

Alternative Hypothesis: There is Endogeneity Factor

Table 5 shows the results for Endogeneity with Prob > chi2 0.057 value is greater than 5% so we cannot reject the null hypothesis.

Tests of Endogeneity for Pakistan Firms (ROA)

Table No: 6

Durbin (score) chi2(1)	= 1.05574 (p = 0.3042)
Wu-Hausman F(1,153)	= 1.01626 (p = 0.3150)

Table 6 shows the results of Endogeneity for the Pakistan firms with the statistics value of durbin and wu-Hausman, those are greater than 5%. So we can say the model of PCSE is corrected for the results.

Instrumental variables (2SLS) regression (ROE)

Table No: 7

Wald chi2(5) = 7.25 Prob > chi2 = 0.2029 R-squared = . Root MSE = 470.47						

ROE	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z 	[95% Conf. Interval]	

IBM	110.0283	114.3799	0.96	0.336	-114.1523	334.2088
BS	-36.77911	27.6259	-1.33	0.183	-90.92489	17.36667
INST	-96.22999	223.6574	-0.43	0.667	-534.5904	342.1304
LVG	-38.36982	85.35729	-0.45	0.653	-205.667	128.9274
FS	-52.48607	56.2909	-0.93	0.351	-162.8142	57.84207
_cons	682.4417	321.9361	2.12	0.034	51.45853	1313.425

We are testing the endogeneity factor in the equation with dependent variable Return on Equity (ROE) with respect to independent variables of corporate governance.

Null Hypothesis: There is no endogeneity Factor

Alternative Hypothesis: There is endogeneity Factor

October 31, 2018

Table 7 shows the results for endogeneity with Prob > chi2 0.2029 value is greater than 5% so we cannot reject the null hypothesis.

Tests of Endogeneity for Pakistan Firms (ROE)

Table No: 8

Durbin (score) chi2(1)	= 1.18245 (p = 0.2769)
Wu-Hausman F(1,153)	= 1.13914 (p = 0.2875)

Table 8 shows the results of Endogeneity for the Pakistan firms with the statistics value of durbin and wu-Hausman, those are greater than 5%. So we can say the model of PCSE is corrected for the results.

Indian Firms Results for Endogeneity Test

Following tables represent the results of Endogeneity in the independent variables of corporate governance with dependent variable Return on Assets in the region of India.

Table No: 9 Instrumental variables (2SLS) regression (ROA)

Wald chi2(5) = 5.55						
Prob > chi2 = 0.3523						
R-squared = .						
Root MSE = .36778						

ROA 	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z 	[95% Conf. Interval]	

IBM 	.0372632	.0311244	1.20	0.231	-.0237395	.0982658
BS 	-.0986958	.0868301	-1.14	0.256	-.2688797	.0714881
INST 	.2443856	.2183004	1.12	0.263	-.1834754	.6722465
FS 	.021719	.0122343	1.78	0.076	-.0022598	.0456978
LVG 	.0224057	.0132346	1.69	0.090	-.0035337	.048345
_cons 	-.2177733	.1348331	-1.62	0.106	-.4820413	.0464947

We are testing the Endogeneity factor in the equation with dependent variable Return on Assets (ROA) with respect to independent variables of corporate governance for Indian companies.

Null Hypothesis: There is no Endogeneity Factor

Alternative Hypothesis: There is Endogeneity Factor

Table 9 shows the results for Endogeneity with Prob > chi2 0.3523 value is greater than 5% so we cannot reject the null hypothesis.

Tests of Endogeneity for Indian Firms (ROA)

Table No: 10

Durbin (score) chi2(1)	= 5.5497 (p = 0.185)
Wu-Hausman F(1,233)	= 5.51537 (p = 0.197)

Table 10 shows the results of Endogeneity for the Pakistan firms with the statistics value of durbin and wu-Hausman, those are greater than 5%. Therefore, we can say the model of PCSE is corrected for the results.

Following tables represent the results of Endogeneity in the independent variables of corporate governance with dependent variable Return on Equity in the region of India.

Table No: 11 Instrumental variables (2SLS) regression (ROE)

October 31, 2018

	Wald chi2(5) = 2.81
	Prob > chi2 = 0.7295
	R-squared = .
	Root MSE = 5.4251

ROE	Coef. Std. Err. z P> z [95% Conf. Interval]

IBM	.5411732 .4727285 1.14 0.252 -.3853577 1.467704
BS	-1.435076 1.333525 -1.08 0.282 -4.048738 1.178585
OWN	4.086043 3.353168 1.22 0.223 -2.486045 10.65813
FS	.2279772 .1757019 1.30 0.194 -.1163922 .5723467
LVG	.010323 .1956753 0.05 0.958 -.3731935 .3938395
_cons	-1.367717 1.933886 -0.71 0.479 -5.158064 2.422629

We are testing the endogeneity factor in the equation with dependent variable Return on Equity (ROE) with respect to independent variables of corporate governance for Indian companies.

Null Hypothesis: There is no endogeneity Factor
Alternative Hypothesis: There is endogeneity Factor

Table 11 shows the results for endogeneity with Prob > chi2 0.7295 value is greater than 5% so we cannot reject the null hypothesis.

Tests of Endogeneity for Indian Firms (ROE)

Table 12

Durbin (score) chi2(1)	= 4.84634 (p = 0.277)
Wu-Hausman F(1,229)	= 4.80119 (p = 0.294)

Table 12 shows the results of Endogeneity for the Pakistan firms with the statistics value of Durbin and Wu-Hausman, those are greater than 5%. Therefore, we can say the model of PCSE is corrected for the results.

Discussion

The study empirically finds out the relation between corporate governance and the firm performance in the regions of Pakistan and India. As following we compare the impact of corporate governance on the firm performance with dependent variable return on asset (ROA) as accounting tool to measure the performance of the firm.

<u>Indian Firms</u>		
ROA	Coef.	P> z
BS	.013231	0.076
CED	.0739651	0.000
OWN	-.0151814	0.720
FS	.0075544	0.077
LVG	.0180609	0.000
IBM	-.0022146	0.519
cons	-.1609693	0.001

<u>Pakistan Firms</u>		
ROA	Coef.	P> z
BS	.0334636	0.003
CED	-.1036083	0.093
OWN	.298373	0.015
FS	-.0399134	0.674
LVG	-.3301502	0.000
IBM	-.0387869	0.000
cons	.2241863	0.704

October 31, 2018

Both above Panel-Corrected Standard Error tables show the comparison between both countries. The firm performance is by corporate governance practices, first variable of the corporate governance is board size which is positively correlated with the firm performance in both regions and next variable is that the CEO duality positive relates in the Indian firms when a CEO possess both position. Conclude performance of the firm will be increased and it goes down when CEO possess both position in Pakistan firms. Ownership structure negative correlated in the Indian firm's performance while positive with Pakistan Firms. Firm's size positive correlated in the Indian Firms while negative correlated in the Pakistan firms. Leverage is positive relation with firm performance in the Indian firms and negative relation with the Pakistan firms. Independent Board Members are negative correlated with the firm performance in both countries firm.

INDIAN FIRMS

ROE	Coef.	P> z
BS	.2059712	0.115
IBM	-.0319009	0.508
CED	1.043706	0.001
OWN	.2514732	0.505
LVG	-.0524196	0.006
FS	.034698	0.502
cons	-.7326307	0.321

PAKISTAN FIRMS

ROE	Coef.	P> z
BS	-.69579	0.000
IBM	-.842	0.237
CEDU	-.353	0.000
OWN	-.2304	0.007
LVG	-.36616	0.001
FS	-.7338	0.164
cons	570.4571	0.000

Return on Equity is another tool to measure the performance of the companies. Both above tables show the relationship between the Corporate Governance and the Firm Performance in the region of Pakistan and India. In Pakistan context with respect to equity corporate Governance is negative related with the firm performance. While Independent board members and leverage is negative relation with the firm performance in India. On the other hand Board Size, CEO duality, Ownership structure and firm size are positive related with the performance of the Indian firms with the accounting tool return on equity.

Implications and Future Research Directions

The study has an important element for researchers, directors of the companies and for the government officials for policy making in corporate governance. Firms that adopt good corporate governance practices, these firms can perform better financial performance for the all stakeholders as well as reduce the agency cost.

References:

- i. Anderson, R. C., & Reeb, D. M. (2003). *Founding-family ownership and firm performance: Evidence from the S&P 500*. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 44(2), 238-286. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1540-6261.00567>
- ii. Arun, T. G., & Turner, J. D. (2003). *Financial sector reforms and corporate governance of banks in developing economies: the Indian experience*. *South Asia Economic Journal*, 4(2), 187-204. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/139156140300400202>
- iii. Baker, H. K., & Anderson, R. (Eds.) (2010). *Corporate Governance: A Synthesis of Theory, Research, and Practice*. New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons Inc.
- iv. Baker, T., & Griffith, S. J. (2010). *Predicting corporate governance risk: Evidence from the Directors' and Officers' liability insurance market*. *Chicago Law Review*, 74, 487.
- v. Balasubramanian, N., Black, B. S., & Khanna, V. (2009). *The relation between firm-level corporate governance and market value: A case study of India*. *Emerging Markets Review*, 11(4), 319-340. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ememar.2010.05.001>
- vi. Bebchuk, L., Cohen, A., & Ferrell, A. (2009). *What matters in corporate governance? Review of Financial Studies*, 22(2), 783-827. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/rfs/hhn099>
- vii. Berle, A., & Means, G. (1932). *The Modern Corporation and Private Property*. New York: Macmillan.
- viii. Bhagat, S., & Bolton, B. (2008). *Corporate governance and firm performance*. *Journal of corporate finance*, 14(3), 257-273. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2008.03.006>
- ix. Brown, L. D., & Caylor, M. L. (2006). *Corporate governance and firm valuation*. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 25(4), 409-434. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccpubpol.2006.05.005>
- x. Choe, J. D., & Lee, D. S. (2010). *The conditional nature of the value of corporate governance*. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 34(2), 350-361. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jbankfin.2009.08.001>

October 31, 2018

- xi. *Claessens, S., Djankov, S., & Lang, L. (2000). The separation of ownership and control in East Asian corporations. Journal of Financial Economics, 58, 81–112. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0304-405X\(00\)00067-2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0304-405X(00)00067-2) 64 S. B. G. C.*
- xii. *Davidson, W. N. (2003). Agency cost, ownership structure and corporate governance mechanisms. Journal of Banking and Finance, 27, 793-816. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4266\(01\)00260-6](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4266(01)00260-6)*

October 31, 2018

- xiii. Davis, J. H., Schoorman, F. D., & Donaldson, L. (1997). *Toward a Stewardship Theory of Management*. *The Academy of Management Review*, 22(1), 20- 47. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMR.1997.9707180258>
- xiv. Denis, D. J., & Kruse, T. A. (2001). *Managerial discipline and corporate restructuring following performance decline*. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 55, 391-424. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0304-405X\(99\)00055-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0304-405X(99)00055-0)
- xv. Doidge, C., Karolyi, A., & Stulz, R. M. (2007). *Why do countries matter so much for corporate governance?* *Journal of financial economics*, 86(1) 1–39. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2006.09.002>
- xvi. Drucker, P.F. (1954). *The Practice of Management*. New York: Harper & Row.
- xvii. Faccio, M., Lang, L., & Young, L. (2001). *Dividends and expropriation*. *American Economic Review*, 91, 54–78.
- xviii. Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). *Separation of ownership and control*. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26, 301-324.
- xix. Gompers, P. A., Ishii, J. L., & Metrick, A. (2003). *Corporate governance and equity prices*. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(1), 107-155. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1162/00335530360535162>
- xx. Hausman, J. (1978). *Specification tests in econometrics*. *Econometrica*, 46, 1251-1271. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/1913827>
- xxi. Hermalin, B. E., & Weisbach, M. S. (2001). *Boards of directors as an endogenously determined institution: A survey of the economic literature*. *FRBNY Economic Policy Review*, 7-26. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3386/w8161>
- xxii. Jensen, M. C. (1993). *The modern industrial revolution, exit, and the failure of internal control systems*. *Journal of Finance*, 48, 831-880. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1993.tb04022.x>
- xxiii. Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. (1976). *Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency cost and ownership structure*. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3, 305-360. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(76\)90026-X](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(76)90026-X)
- xxiv. Kirkpatrick, G. (2009). *The corporate governance lesson from the financial crisis: OECD Report*. *Financial Market Trends*, 1, 2-55.
- xxv. Klapper, L. F., & Love, I. (2004). *Corporate governance, investor protection, and performance in emerging markets*. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 10(5), 703-728. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1199\(03\)00046-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1199(03)00046-4)
- xxvi. La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., & Shleifer, A. (2008). *The economic consequences of legal origins*. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 46(2), 285-332. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1257/jel.46.2.285>
- xxvii. Lipton, M., & Lorsch, J. W. (1992). *A modest proposal for improved corporate governance*. *The Business Lawyer*, 59-77.
- xxviii. Love, I. (2010). *Corporate governance and performance around the world: What we know and what we don't*. *The World Bank Research Observer*, lkp030. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/wbro/lkp030>
- xxix. Macey, J. R. (2008). *Corporate Governance: Promises Kept, Promises Broken*. Princeton, NJ, USA: Princeton University Press.
- xxx. Mallin, C. (2008). *Institutional shareholders: Their role in the shaping of corporate governance*. *International Journal of Corporate Governance*, 1(1), 97-105. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/IJCG.2008.017652>
- xxxi. Mohanty, P. (2004). *Institutional investors and corporate governance in India*. Retrieved from <http://ssrn.com/abstract=353820>. *Corporate Governance and Firm Performance* 65
- xxxii. Morck, R. K. (Ed.). (2007). *A history of corporate governance around the world: family business groups to professional managers*. University of Chicago Press.
- xxxiii. OECD (2004). *OECD Principles of Corporate Governance*. Retrieved from <http://www.oecd.org/dataoecd/32/18/31557724.pdf>.
- xxxiv. Peasnell, K.V., Pope, P.F., & Young, S. (2003). *Managerial equity ownership and the demand for outside directors*. Working paper, Lancaster University.
- xxxv. Reinganum, M. R. (2009). *Setting national priorities: Financial challenges facing the Obama administration*. *Financial Analysts Journal*, 65(2), 32-48. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2469/faj.v65.n2.7>
- xxxvi. Saravanan, P. (2012). *Corporate governance and company performance: A study with reference to manufacturing firms in India*. *Journal of Political Economy*, 12(1), 155-175. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2063677>
- xxxvii. Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. (1986). *Large shareholders and corporate control*. *Journal of Political Economy*, 95, 461–488.
- xxxviii. Srinivasan, P., & Srinivasan, V. (2011). *Status of corporate governance research in India: An exploratory study*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 10, 50-75.
- xxxix. Stock, J. H., & Yogo, M. (2004). *Testing for weak instruments in linear IV regression*. In Andrews, D.W.K. and Stock, J.H. (eds.), *Identification and Inference for Econometric Models: Essays in Honor of Thomas J. Rothenberg*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- xl. Stulz, R.M. (1990). *Managerial discretion and optimal financing policies*. *Journal of Financial Economics*, (26), 3-27. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(90\)90011-N](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(90)90011-N)
- xli. Vo, D., & Phan, T. (2013). *Corporate governance and firm performance: Empirical evidence from Vietnam*. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 78, 210-226.

October 31, 2018

- xlii. Young, M. N., Peng, M. W., Ahlstrom, D., Bruton, G. D., & Jiang, Y. (2008). *Corporate governance in emerging economies: A review of the Principal-Principal perspective*. *Journal of Management Studies*, 45(1), 196-220. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2007.00752.x>